

CAUSES OF FATAL OUTCOMES IN COMBINED TRAUMA AND THEIR FORENSIC MEDICAL EVALUATION

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Abstract. *This study aims to fill the gap in causes of fatal outcomes in combined trauma which were analyzed and studied to develop preventive measures aimed at reducing mortality. The analysis of the materials indicated that the severity of modern combined trauma leads to a fatal outcome in half of the cases during the earliest period. At the same time, the data revealed various mechanisms of the development of several severe post-traumatic complications, the prevention of which could help reduce mortality in these cases.*

Keywords: *causes of fatal outcomes, combined trauma, mortality, complications.*

Relevance: There is growing interest in multiple and simultaneous injuries provoking a specific body response characterized by the severity of the trauma and a high percentage of fatal outcomes [1]. Conventional trauma treatment principles and approaches for combined trauma are insufficient. Injuries to isolated segments typically result in localized pain in the damaged area and loss (or impairment) of function in one area, which may not significantly limit the patient's ability to engage in daily activities. Combined trauma leads to traumatic disease—a general severe and rapidly developing bodily reaction [3]. The body's own forces are insufficient for recovery and healing. Often, even large-scale medical interventions do not yield the desired effect. In the case of combined trauma, the prognosis of the injury itself becomes secondary [2]. The main question is whether the patient's life can be saved. Combined trauma is characterized by shock, where the body's ability to maintain vital functions diminishes. If the risk of death in the acute period is overcome, combined trauma will typically follow an unfavorable course. Complications are more likely, numerous, and the recovery period is prolonged [4]. Combined trauma results from high-energy injuries. It is the application of great force that leads to multiple fractures and internal organ injuries. The most common causes are: road traffic accidents, falls from a height, building collapses, industrial injuries, and war-related injuries [7]. The simultaneity of injuries is more important than their specific cause. Combined trauma should be defined without delving into formalism: the severity of the injuries is evaluated individually, with at least one component of the trauma being severe [5]. For example, a fractured toe and a scalped hand wound would not be considered combined trauma. Issues of diagnosis and medical tactics for combined injuries, as well as mortality, remain contentious, and the high mortality rate and significant number of unsatisfactory outcomes make them one of the most pressing issues in modern traumatology and forensic medicine [6]. Most of these injuries are accompanied by severe shock and significant blood loss, requiring immediate resuscitative and tactical measures. Diagnostic errors, incorrect or often untimely surgical decisions, and treatment protocols, along with the severity of the patient's condition, are often the main causes of high mortality and disability.

The aim of study: To study the causes of fatal outcomes in combined trauma and develop preventive measures to reduce mortality.

Materials and Methods: Fifty-three forensic medical reports on combined trauma deaths were analyzed, conducted at Tashkent branch of the National Research Center for Forensic

Medical Expertise over the period of 2020–2023. In 50.2% of cases, the injuries were sustained due to road traffic accidents, 21.6% from falls from height, and 28.2% from blunt force trauma. Seventy percent of the injured were male, mostly aged 30 to 50 years, while the rest were women. Individuals under 20 years old accounted for 3.1% of the total studied. Deaths under 30 years made up 16.7%, under 40 years—18.1%, under 50 years—20.5%, under 60 years—10.9%, under 70 years—13.7%, and over 70 years—17%. The predominance of male fatalities can be explained by a higher incidence of alcohol intoxication at the time of injury.

Results and Discussion: The analyzed material shows the severity of the traumatic injuries, with injuries to two or three areas of the body being most common. Isolated injuries to the chest or abdominal organs made up only 17.4% of the study sample. Closed injuries to the chest and abdominal organs combined with multiple fractures of the chest, pelvic bones, and less frequently, limbs, made up 66% of the material.

It is well known that the causes of death were analyzed based on clinical and morphological manifestations of trauma and its leading complications at various stages after the injury. The causes of death were compared with the time of death.

In the study, the following causes of death were identified in cases of combined trauma: shock and blood loss—42.6%, brain injury—22%, pneumonia—12%, acute respiratory failure—6.6%, sepsis—4.3%, peritonitis—2.1%, anaerobic infection—0.6%, fat embolism—1.9%, pulmonary embolism—1.8%, and other causes—6.1%.

As a result of the timing of death due to shock and blood loss showed an early onset of death, within the first 3 hours after admission to the hospital, in half of the cases. These numbers reflect the severity of the trauma, where intensive pre-hospital treatment only prolongs life temporarily. The victims in this group could be considered to have received injuries incompatible with life. In this group, fatalities occurred early from combined trauma involving the chest, abdomen, and pelvis, resulting in massive blood loss, highlighting the significance of shock in causing death.

According to the second group of causes of death of victims included complications of craniocerebral trauma combined with damage to the chest and abdominal organs. Without dwelling on the details of complications of craniocerebral trauma, it is necessary to note only the importance of a number of typical complications in the genesis of death. In addition to the actual traumatic damage to the brain and its membranes, significant dislocation of the brain stem structures, often accompanied by secondary hemorrhages, and filling the ventricles of the brain with blood can also be of great importance in the onset of death. These complications develop mainly in the first 3 days after the injury and require emergency treatment.

There is a need for fatal complications of a more remote period of injury deserve special attention. In the first place among these complications is pulmonary pathology. It includes 2 groups of complications. The first is pneumonia, which accounts for 12% of the studied material. The second group includes acute respiratory failure, which requires vigorous treatment and accounts for 6.6% of the causes of death. These complications occur from the third day and later after the injury and are often accompanied in the clinic by a vivid picture of acute respiratory failure. Pneumonia in patients with TBI develops at an earlier stage, it can be detected already at the end of the second day after the injury.

This study aims to fill the gap in great importance among the causes of death in combined trauma with purulent complications, accounting for about 7% of cases. Peritonitis occurs by the

end of the 1st or 2nd week after receiving an injury and damage to the abdominal organs and pelvis.

Over the past few years rare complications include anaerobic infection, which accounts for 0.6% of the causes of death. It was detected in those who died on the 2nd-3rd day after receiving an injury with extensive crushing of soft tissues, accompanied by bacterial contamination of the soft tissues of the limbs and pelvis. In 3.7% of the studied material, embolic complications were the causes of death of the victims. Half of them were fat embolism, developing on the 2nd-3rd day after the injury with fractures of the pelvic bones and limbs. They were accompanied by a typical clinical picture, characteristic morphology and were always confirmed by histological studies of organs, including the brain.

Conclusions:

The severity of modern combined trauma leads to a fatal outcome in half of the cases in the early period.

The presented data reveals various mechanisms behind the development of severe post-traumatic complications, the prevention of which could help reduce mortality in combined trauma.

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